

**THE IMPACT OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE ON THE PROFESSIONAL
COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS**

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Annotation: The article briefly discusses the important aspects of developing a health culture in the modern education system, especially in improving the professional competencies of students in the pedagogical field. It is stated that the healthy lifestyle of teachers working in the pedagogical field helps them develop their culture and achieve successful results in their professional activities.

**BO‘LAJAK O‘QITUVCHILARDA SOG‘LOM TURMUSH TARZINING
KASBIY KOMPETENTLIGIGA TA‘SIRI**

Namangan davlat universiteti San‘at va sport fakulteti
Jismoniy tarbiya va amaliy sport turlari kafedrası o‘qituvchisi

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Anatatsiya: Maqolada zamonaviy ta‘lim tizimida salomatlik madaniyatini rivojlantirish, ayniqsa, pedagogik faoliyat yo‘nalishidagi talabalarning professional kompetensiyalarini oshirishda muhim jihatlari haqida qisqacha yoritib o‘tilgan. Pedagogika yo‘nalishida faoliyat olib boruvchi o‘qituvchilarning sog‘lom turmush tarsi asosida hayot kechirishlari ularda madaniyatini rivojlantirish, ularning professional faoliyatlarida muvaffaqiyatli natijalarga erishishga yordam berishi bayon qilingan.

**ВЛИЯНИЕ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ НА ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНУЮ
КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТЬ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ**

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Аннотация: В статье кратко рассматриваются важные аспекты развития культуры здорового образа жизни в современной системе образования, особенно в контексте повышения профессиональной компетентности студентов педагогической сферы. Утверждается, что здоровый образ жизни преподавателей, работающих в педагогической сфере, способствует развитию их культуры и достижению успешных результатов в профессиональной деятельности.

The formation of a healthy lifestyle among future teachers is considered one of the important factors for the development of society. This is because a teacher is not only a provider of knowledge but also a person who directly influences the formation of future generations. Therefore, students studying in pedagogical higher education institutions should be able to follow a healthy lifestyle, integrate it into their own lives, and teach it to their future students. A healthy lifestyle is a combination of factors that ensure a person's physical well-being, psychological stability, and social welfare. It includes proper nutrition, physical activity, stress management, rational use of digital technologies (such as mobile phones, computers, and other devices), adherence to work-rest balance, and attention to personal hygiene. The effective organization of this process should be carried out based on pedagogical, psychological, and physiological principles.

Developing a culture of health preservation among teachers working in the field of pedagogy contributes to achieving successful results in their professional activities. Scientific research conducted in Uzbekistan on preserving the health of pedagogical staff is aimed at eliminating shortcomings existing in the national education system. Developing innovative methodologies for improving the health culture of students and teachers, while considering international experience, creates opportunities for establishing practical approaches.

This dissertation research serves, to a certain extent, the implementation of tasks outlined in several normative-legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including Presidential Decree No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, *“On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026”*; Presidential Decree No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019, *“On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”*; Resolution No. 1059 of the Cabinet of Ministers dated December 31, 2019, *“On Approval of the Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education and Measures for Its*

Implementation”; and Presidential Decree No. PF-6155 dated February 3, 2021, “*On the State Program for the Implementation of the Action Strategy on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017–2021 within the Year of Supporting Youth and Strengthening Public Health.*”

A healthy lifestyle (HL) is a set of habits, behaviors, and regulated activities aimed at maintaining and strengthening one’s health, understanding one’s body, and developing physical qualities. It may also be regarded as a means of ensuring physical comfort, mental stability, and broad healthy thinking. Achieving it is not a highly complicated process, yet it is especially important for future teachers. Only when a teacher possesses strong mental, intellectual, social, and physical health can they effectively provide students with knowledge based on healthy values and constructive thinking.

In modern society, the issue of forming a healthy lifestyle has become highly relevant. Today, large-scale reforms are being implemented in our country to fundamentally improve the education system, strengthen the material and technical base of educational institutions, enrich methodological support in accordance with modern requirements, and create necessary conditions for developing healthy lifestyle habits among students. These reforms also contribute to improving the content and quality of extracurricular activities, increasing their attractiveness, and strengthening learners’ interest and engagement in such activities.

In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, No. PQ-4312 dated May 8, 2019, “*On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030,*” established strategic foundations for continuously developing the education system and raising a healthy, comprehensively developed generation. This document places special emphasis on increasing children’s physical activity, fostering healthy lifestyle habits from an early age, and widely introducing sports and active games.

A healthy lifestyle contributes to maintaining and strengthening human health, increasing work capacity, and ensuring active longevity. Considerable attention is paid to this issue in the Republic of Uzbekistan, where a number of state-level measures are being implemented. For instance, Presidential Decree No. PF-6099, adopted on October 30, 2020, defined tasks related to promoting a healthy lifestyle and developing mass sports. However, problems related to unhealthy lifestyles still persist among the population. According to 2023 data, 30% of Uzbekistan’s population follows an unhealthy lifestyle, 16.5% consume tobacco products, 4.7% consume alcohol, and 16% do not consume sufficient fruits and vegetables [5]. Such indicators

are also concerning for future teachers, who are expected to educate future generations. Guiding future teachers toward a healthy lifestyle affects not only their personal health but also the healthy development of the younger generation they will teach. Therefore, studying the pedagogical, psychological, and physiological principles of forming a healthy lifestyle among future teachers has significant scientific and practical importance.

From a pedagogical perspective, teaching future teachers to adopt a healthy lifestyle should be systematic and continuous, reinforced not only through theoretical knowledge but also through practical activities. It should be based on an individualized approach, considering the needs of each student and developing their conscious attitude toward healthy living. Healthy lifestyle habits should not be limited solely to physical education classes but should be integrated into various disciplines. Subjects such as biology, general psychology, personality pedagogy, medicine, physiology, and hygiene play an important role in teaching the foundations of a healthy lifestyle. In addition, increasing students' internal motivation, developing a sense of responsibility for their own health, improving body awareness, and strengthening practical skills are essential.

A teacher's theoretical preparedness for health-promoting activities is often understood as a certain combination of psychological, pedagogical, and specialized knowledge. However, the development of knowledge and understanding is not an end in itself. A teacher can be considered to have developed health-preserving competence only when they not only possess knowledge about health, healthy lifestyles, and health-promoting technologies, and understand the value of health, but also apply these values, knowledge, and motivations in practice concerning both their own health and the health of their students.

According to medical and scientific research, 50–55% of human health and life expectancy depends on lifestyle. The remaining part is influenced by heredity (20–25%), environmental factors (15–20%), and medical services (8–10%). In this regard, I propose a simple and understandable diagram illustrating the normative 24-hour indicators for maintaining a healthy lifestyle.

The normative indicators of a healthy lifestyle, which constitute approximately 50% of factors affecting human health, are as follows.

Figure 1.

HEALTHY LIFESTYLE (24 Hours)

- zzz Sleep (7–9 hours) → 10–12.5%
- 🍏 Nutrition / Healthy Eating → 7.5–10%
- 🏃 Physical Activity → 10–12.5%
- ☐ Personal Hygiene and Daily Routine → 5–7.5%
- 📚 Work / Study → 7.5–12.5%
- ☐ Rest / Mental Relaxation → 5–7.5%
- 🚫 Avoidance of Harmful Habits → 5%

Such an organized and balanced lifestyle contributes to the teacher's development not only physically but also psychologically and professionally. Adequate sleep and proper nutrition strengthen overall health, which helps the teacher remain energetic and attentive during the teaching process. Physical activity increases energy levels and reduces stress.

Through the time allocated to work and study, the teacher continuously works on self-improvement, developing knowledge and professional skills. At the same time, allocating

sufficient time for rest and mental relaxation prevents exhaustion and helps avoid professional burnout.

As a result, a teacher who follows such a lifestyle develops into a person who:

- has a strong command of their subject area;
- can work effectively with students;
- maintains healthy and positive thinking;
- becomes beneficial to society and serves as a role model for others.

In short, a healthy lifestyle transforms a future teacher into a well-rounded and successful educator.

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